

INSECURITY IN NORTHERN NIGERIA AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR FOOD SECURITY IN NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18470659>

Keywords

Insecurity, armed banditry, Terrorists, Food Security, Food Insecurity, Criminal Gangs, forced migration, fatalities, humanitarian crisis.

Abstract: *Against the backdrop of increasing security challenges such as terrorism, insurgency, herders/farmers conflict, armed banditry and kidnapping in northern Nigeria. The paper critically examines the implications of these challenges to food security in Nigeria, using a secondary research approach and the human security theory of analysis. It found that despite government efforts using military offensives across the affected areas, several non-state armed groups seem unperturbed in the region, and have continued to unleash severe damage in the region, particularly the rural communities who are predominantly farmers, causing deaths, dislocations and displacement of livelihoods and agricultural productivity. Moreover, the northern Nigerian is the major supplier of food produce in Nigeria, with about 75 per cent of Nigeria's staple food, such as rice, maize, beans, yams, potatoes, onions, beef, tomatoes, pepper, etc. The implications have been the increasing shortage of food production, supply and access across the country. The study recommended, among others, that the federal government should ensure collaboration between security agencies, community leaders, and local informants to enhance intelligence gathering, threat detection, and conflict prevention; state governments, alongside community leaders should show serious commitment to ending insecurity in their various states by collaborating with federal government security forces to contain the activities of these non-state armed groups.*

Introduction

Over the past decade, insecurity caused by the resurgence of terrorism, cattle rustling, armed banditry and kidnapping for ransom has taken

centre stage in the theatre of Nigeria's security challenges, spiralling and cutting across the entire country with its associated fatalities and humanitarian catastrophes. Most affected

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among the six geographical zones are the three northern zones, including northcentral, northeast and northwest, where the majority of the forests in the rural communities have been converted into a haven for armed bandits and terrorists with severe consequences on the lives and livelihoods of the local farming communities in the region. Reports from notable international conflict monitors like the Armed Conflict Location and Event Data Project (ACLED) (2023) noted that there is a high incidence of violent attacks in northern Nigeria over the past decade compared to southern Nigeria, particularly in the Northwest and North Central regions, driven by banditry, kidnappings, farmer-herder conflicts, and terrorist activities, confirming a disproportionate burden of violence in the north compared to other parts of the country. Similarly, the Nigeria Watch Thirteenth Report on Violence in Nigeria (2023) noted that between 2006 and 2023, about 196,737 people lost their lives in 40,725 lethal incidents across the 36 Nigerian states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), with northern Nigeria accounting for approximately 75 per cent of the fatalities.

Specifically, northern states like Benue, Borno, Kaduna, Niger, Plateau, Sokoto, and Zamfara have been noted to have experienced more violent attacks and the highest number of deaths in recent times, making them the most troubled states in Nigeria (Nigeria Violent Conflict Monthly Bulletin, 2024). In early 2023, Zamfara and Sokoto states, for instance, recorded deaths of 147 farmers, with some reportedly kidnapped

while some went missing after leaving their homes for survival to avoid attack after losing their farms and sources of income to attackers (Vatican News, 2023). In addition, the majority of farmers in many communities across the northern region, where the bandits and terrorists hold sway, have been subjected to paying royalties in the form of taxes to the bandits' leaders before they could plant or harvest their crops. In Zamfara, bandits impose taxes ranging from N100,000 to N300,000 on farmers to gain access to their farmland and cultivate or harvest crops. Similarly, residents of Ukum Local Government Area (LGA) in Benue State reported that farmers had sold their farm produce to raise N20 million to meet a tax of N50,000 imposed by bandits, with each household contributing N50,000 to meet the deadline (Punch, 2024).

In response, the federal and state governments have made concerted efforts to address the challenges, including Military Joint Task Force Operations, special police operations, community engagement, peace-building initiatives, and negotiations with criminals to surrender their weapons and embrace peace. However, these have not yielded the expected results, as the trend of attacks on the rural farming communities has remained on the increase, with records of fatalities, displacements and sacking of farming communities making headlines on national dailies. Apart from the threats to lives and properties, the impacts on food availability, access and stability are obvious. For instance, a 2025 report from the International Food Policy

Research Institute (IFPRI) highlights that insecurity has disrupted supply chains and reduced farmers' incomes.

A recent report from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) warned in October 2025 that persistent threats from insecurity in northern Nigeria continue to put millions at risk of hunger. This is supported by a joint report by the FAO and the World Food Programme (WFP), which projected that in November 2025, millions could face critical food insecurity in 16 Northern states and the FCT due to the ongoing security challenges. In the same vein, another recent report indicated that over 34 million Nigerians could be at risk of a food crisis by mid-2026, citing insecurity, high input costs, and weak rural economies as key drivers (The Nation Newspaper, 2025). Against the background of these issues, this study sets out to critically examine the rising insecurity in northern Nigeria and to draw out its implications for food security in Nigeria by analysing its impacts on food availability, access, utilisation and food stability in Nigeria.

Methodology

The study is a qualitative research design that relied largely on the use of documented evidence from secondary sources such as extant literature and studies, newspapers, and magazines. It also included the use of trend analysis from international and national conflict monitors. While the relevant literature were critically reviewed to demonstrate the novelty of the work and to position the paper in the broader academic debate, the reports from the media, international monitors and documented

evidence were qualitatively analysed, using the content analysis technique. This ensured a systematic extraction of the relevant contents relating to the study, while offering both quantitative and qualitative insights into the study.

Conceptual Clarification: Insecurity and Food Security

Insecurity

The Collins English Dictionary (2025) defines insecurity as “a feeling of a lack of confidence or assurance, leading to self-doubt and anxiety about oneself and one’s abilities, relationships, or future, or a state of being unsafe or unstable” It includes job insecurity, financial insecurity, or a lack of safety from harm.” According to the American Psychological Association’s Dictionary of Psychology (2018), it is a sense of inadequacy in one or more areas of human life, a lack of self-confidence, and difficulty coping with uncertainty, abandonment, failure, or hardship. It further noted that Individuals might also feel shy and insecure about goals, abilities, or relationships, among other challenges. This means that insecurity can look different for everyone, depending on the factors triggering such feelings. However, whichever way one feels about insecurity, it is either a psychological state or a physical state of fear or anxiety that makes one or a segment/segment of society feel unsafe and uncertain about their life while sensing danger or threat.

The above understanding of insecurity was upheld by Beland (2007), who describes insecurity as a state of fear or anxiety that stems from a concrete or alleged lack of protection.

However, Beland's definition reflects more of physical insecurity than psychological, which is the most visible form of insecurity, and it triggers many other forms of insecurity, such as economic, social and food insecurity. This view is upheld by Siegel (2010), who asserts that the feeling of anxiety that people express results from their vulnerability to threat and harm. Siegel further insists that this vulnerability is coterminous with crisis, conflict, or even war, which implies that the feeling of collective insecurity in every society is associated with conflict, crisis and war.

The above assertion is supported by Elrol, Simsek and Munir (2010), who argue that certain external realities, such as socioeconomic ill-being, violence, and war, are major instigators of insecurity threatening the collective security and well-being of the people. They noted that these realities, particularly violence and war, affect all domains of human wellbeing, inflicting a feeling of hopelessness and helplessness. The causes and sources of insecurity, as captured by Achumba, Ighomereho and Akpor-Robaro (2013) include lack of institutional capacity resulting in government failure, ethnic-religious conflicts, pervasive material inequalities, poverty and unfairness, conflict of perception between the public and government, weak security systems, and loss of social-cultural and communal value systems. Also included are porous borders leading to the influx of small arms and light weapons (SALWs) proliferation, and the easy availability of these weapons in the hands of non-state armed groups like terrorists, militants

and bandits has enabled insecurity (Hazen & Horner, 2007).

In addition, Adegbami (2013) points out that collective insecurity in every society is politically instigated, noting that political factors are the major drivers that instigate other forms of insecurity that lead to armed conflict. These include unemployment and poverty, elite exploitation of ethnicity and religion, corruption, bad governance, weak security apparatus, porous borders, marginalization and inequality. He further insists that these factors manifest in forms such as terrorism, banditry, communal clashes, insurgency, militancy, kidnapping for ransom, ethnic agitations, destruction of property, and fear, all of which threaten public safety and stability. This assertion is supported by Daramola (2023), who posits that insecurity can also manifest as an individual's lack of self-confidence and a feeling of being unprotected, or as a broader societal condition of instability, risk, and threat to peace, stability, and human well-being, and its causes are often linked to political factors. This perception attaches importance to political factors as major drivers of insecurity. However, other factors such as economic, social, and ethno-religious play major roles in creating insecurity.

In a more specific approach, the United Nations Trust Fund for Human Security (2018) identifies various factors that can cause collective insecurity in the contemporary world, stressing that natural disasters, violent conflicts, persistent poverty, epidemics, and economic downturns, which impose hardships and

undercut prospects for peace and stability, cannot be exempted. It further stresses that these factors may have their unique attributes, but they are often interconnected, as one may likely trigger the other; just like a violent attack or economic downturn, can rapidly spill over and worsen others or create a sense of insecurity across the board. In Nigeria, the violent attacks and conflicts caused by non-state armed groups such as Boko Haram, ISWAP, Lakurawa, and other criminal groups in the north have resulted in insecurity, affecting not only the stability of the country but all other sectors of life, including food security. Meanwhile, the search for strategies to contain the challenges continues, one of the reasons that guided this study.

Food Security

Reflecting on the concept of food security, Reutlinger (1985) emphasizes food security as access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food for an active, healthy life, focusing on food availability and the ability to acquire it, particularly for developing countries. He noted the importance of both having food present and people's ability to access it economically. He also recognizes the complexities of this issue and the magnitude of food insecurity and proposes remedies like a food import bill insurance scheme and a combination of financial schemes and grain buffer stocks to address it, arguing that food security should not depend solely on global supply stabilization. This view is upheld by the World Bank (1986) when it insists that food security is a condition in which all have access to sufficient food to live

a healthy and productive life, while also emphasizing the quality of the food.

The above view was elaborated by the 1996 World Food Summit, which states that food security means that all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life. It is not just about having enough food available, but also ensuring everyone can afford and access it, and that the food is of good quality. It is on this basis that Davies (2009) sees food security as encompassing other factors like the nutritional values of the food available, the possession of the means to acquire and reasonable sustainability in its supply (Davies, 2009). What this implies is that for a nation to be food secure or have food security, food must be available, it must be accessible, it must be sufficient for an active and healthy life, and it must be fully utilized to the satisfaction of the people. This contention re-echoes Maxwell and Frankenberg's (1992) position that a country and its people are food secure when their food system operates in such a way as to remove the fear that there will not be enough to eat.

Drawing from the foregoing contentions, Agbede (2008) describes national food security as a world in which the majority of households, communities, or the Nigerian populace have economic and physical access to food that is adequate in quantity and quality for a healthy life at all times through agricultural growth, development and poverty eradication. It is clear from these contentions that food security requires that all, even the poor and vulnerable,

have undeniable access to quality food to eat. The protracted violent attack by armed bandits and terrorist groups in northern Nigeria has created significant fear and insecurity, resulting in acute food insecurity, in which the majority of the population of the country can hardly afford a decent meal in a day. It therefore requires the partnership of all stakeholders, especially the federal government, the respective states, local governments and communities, Faith-based and civil society organizations and businesses to bring about the desired peace and security across the affected regions and to revamp the deteriorating food security in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on human security theory. The human security theory is one of the modern theories of security that shifts the focus of security from the state to the individual, emphasising protection from threats such as poverty, disease, hunger, and environmental degradation, alongside traditional threats like violence. Its doctrinal kernel is that human security is the most important element of national security, which must be protected at all costs by the State rather than the emphasis on state security. Key proponents of human security theory include economists Amartya Sen, former Costa Rican President Oscar Arias, and academics like Mary Mack, who developed and promoted its multifaceted approach, and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), which first formalized the concept in its 1994 Human Development Report.

The UNDP (1994) report defines it as freedom from fear and freedom from want for all people,

ultimately aiming to ensure their dignity, survival, and well-being. It stresses safety from chronic threats such as hunger, diseases, oppression and protection from sudden and hurtful impacts in the patterns of everyday life. This view was upheld and elaborated by Amartya Sen (2000), who defines it as “the protection of the vital core of all human lives in ways that enhance human freedoms and human fulfilment”. This involves both protecting people from critical, pervasive threats and empowering them to take action to prevent and mitigate these threats. The goal is to go beyond state-centric security and focus on individual well-being, safeguarding freedoms from fear and want to ensure that lives are humane and worth living (Alkira, 2002). The worsening food security threatening humanity in Nigeria falls within the purview of human security calculus and demands the protection of people rather than the security of the government and territories. It is on this basis that the study adopts the human security theory as the most suitable theoretical framework for analysing insecurity in northern Nigeria and its impact on food security in Nigeria. In addition, its multisectoral approach, which addresses diverse threats such as poverty, disease, hunger, and environmental degradation, provides a comprehensive lens to understand how insecurity directly undermines food production, disrupts livelihoods, and exacerbates hunger in the Nigerian context.

Northern Nigeria and Insecurity

Northern Nigeria is a term used to describe the geographical area that covers all the states in

Nigeria's north along the regional line to differentiate it from the southern region. It constitutes three of Nigeria's six geopolitical zones: the Northcentral, Northeast and Northwest, which include a total of 19 states: Adamawa, Bauchi, Benue, Borno, Gombe, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, and Zamfara, and the Federal Capital Territory. Historically, it was a British protectorate encompassing the powerful Sokoto Caliphate and parts of the former Bornu Empire before the 1914 amalgamation of regions into the Colony and Protectorate of Nigeria (Oladunni et al. 2022). The region is diverse, with a majority Muslim population, numerous ethnic groups including the Hausa and Fulani, and significant agricultural resources.

Northern Nigeria is characterised by a vast, arid-to-semi-arid landscape of savannahs and deserts, with a significant land area that constitutes over 70 per cent of the total land mass of Nigeria (Almu et al, 2019). The population of northern Nigeria, according to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) report of 2022, was estimated at 216,783,381. In addition, the National Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) survey conducted by NBS in 2022 revealed that 65 per cent of the multidimensionally poor population (86 million people) lived in the North, compared to 35 per cent (nearly 47 million people) in the South, suggesting a larger proportion of the population resides in the North including a higher population of poor people.

The mainstay of northern Nigeria's historical and continued economy is agriculture, featuring major crops like groundnuts and cotton, alongside other significant activities such as commerce, mining, and industries. Before the rise of the oil sector, agriculture, especially the renowned groundnut pyramids of Kano, was the dominant economic activity, providing valuable export earnings and livelihoods for a larger part of the population (Ibrahim, 2019). The region contributes significantly to Nigeria's food supply through its extensive production of staples like millet, sorghum, cowpeas, rice, and yams, as well as livestock such as cattle, sheep, and goats, and products like shea nuts, groundnuts, and fish. A 2019 survey observed that northern Nigeria depend so much on agricultural livelihoods than the rest of the country, with 84 per cent of households in the northeast alone engaging in crop production and 69 per cent raising livestock. Additionally, 70 per cent of households' food in Nigeria came from the north (Oladunni et al, 2022). However, factors such as conflict, climate change, poor infrastructure, and rising costs have increasingly hampered the region's ability to achieve its agricultural capability to improve its economy and expected food supply potential for Nigerians.

The most disturbing among these factors are armed banditry, terrorism and kidnapping for ransom, which have been on the increase across the region, shattering thousands of lives, destroying farmlands and agricultural products worth billions of naira, and displacing people from their farmlands and ancestral homes. The

SBM 2022 Intelligence report highlighted the severe impact of escalating violence on Nigeria’s agricultural sectors, revealing that over 1,356 farmers have been killed across the country, with the majority of these deaths occurring in the northern regions (Nature News, 247, 2024). It noted that the violence driven by banditry and widespread insecurity in the north has severely disrupted farming activities, contributing to the nation’s worsening food crisis.

Equally, many people have been abducted and millions displaced in the same year in places like Borno, Kaduna, Katsina, Kebbi, Niger, Sokoto and Zamfara, causing people to flee their ancestral home and farmlands to states where there was relative peace (Adebajo, 2023). The SB Miller (SBM) (2024) Intelligence noted that of the 1,130 reported kidnapping cases across

the country between July 2023 and June 2024, Zamfara, Kaduna, and Katsina have the highest numbers of incidents and victims. Zamfara recorded 132 incidents with 1,639 victims, Kaduna reported 113 incidents with 1,113 victims, and Katsina had 119 incidents with 887 victims (SBM 2024). Sadly, kidnapping has become more lethal in the region, with an average of one person killed each time there is an attempted kidnapping (SBM, 2024). Unfortunately, the trend of attacks and fatalities, including kidnapping, has been on the increase, ranking higher than other parts of the country, with far-reaching implications on livelihoods and agricultural productivity in the region. Figure 1 below shows the number of media-reported killings in Nigeria in the third quarter of 2023 by zone.

Figure 1: Number of Media Reported Killings in Nigeria in Q3 by Zones

Source: SBM Intelligence | Chart: Dataphyte

The above statistics in Figure 1 show that out of the 1,718 deaths recorded within the Q3 (July-September), the northern region (Northeast, Northwest and North-Central) recorded 1,441

deaths. Of the total 1,718 deaths reported in Q3, civilians accounted for 529, security personnel accounted for 72 deaths, while the number of vigilantes who lost their lives was 22. Non-state

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armed groups such as Boko Haram and armed bandits accounted for the deaths in the northern region (SBM Intelligence, 2022).

Similarly, extant studies such as Ukaeje (2021), Lekan et al 2022; and Okoli et al (2024) also noted that the northern region is dominating insecurity in Nigeria, with worst affected states being Katsina, Kaduna, Zamfara, Sokoto and Kebbi in Northwest; Niger, Plateau, and Benue states in North-central; and Borno, Bauchi and Taraba in the Northeast. They stressed that the majority of the attacks are in the rural communities, with thousands of persons

confirmed dead and millions displaced or forced to relocate for their safety and survival. Also recorded are the deadly intercommunal conflict and organized crime in states like Katsina, Sokoto and Zamfara that have led to the displacement of more than 200,000 persons and the death and disappearance of thousands (UNOCHA, 2020). This is supported by the compilation of incidents of attacks and fatalities from the ACLED Database and Hum Angle reports in 2023, respectively, as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Trend of Violence Across Nigeria by Geopolitical Zone (2022-2023)

Geo-Political Zones	Incident s In 2022	Fatalities In 2022	Incident s In 2023	Fatalities In 2023	Differences In Incidents	Differenc es In Fatalities
North-central	912	2,350	857	1,713	-55	-637
Northeast	750	3,040	823	3,271	+73	+231
Northwest	1,100	3,296	971	2,073	-129	-1223
South-south	514	368	588	360	+74	-8
Southeast	635	707	533	470	-102	-237
Southwest	614	251	554	232	-60	-119

Source: Author’s compilation from ACLED Database (2023) and Hum Angle (2023)

Table 1 above on the trend of violence across Nigeria from 2022 to 2023 compares the number of violent incidents and deaths in 2022 to 2023 across Nigeria’s six geopolitical zones, showing the northern region as the worst hit at 15,743 deaths and 5,413 incidents. While the south recorded a total of 2,388 deaths and 3,438 incidents. In geo-specifics, the Northeast

recorded 1,573 incidents with 6,311 deaths within the period, while the Northwest recorded 2,071 incidents with 5,369 deaths, indicating that the Northwest led in the number of attacks, while the Northeast scored higher in the number of fatalities. The North-central followed up with 1,769 incidents and 4,063 fatalities. The Southeast region, on the other hand, took the lead in the south, due to the activities of

separatist Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and Unknown Gunmen (UGM), which have been associated with violent clashes with security agencies.

The IPI Global Observatory Report (2024) noted that the majority of the attacks in the northern region are carried out in the rural communities where the majority of the residents are predominantly agrarian farmers with little or no security protection. It noted that armed banditry is taking a toll in the Northwest, with Zamfara and Kaduna the worst hit. The

report further revealed that there are about 30,000 bandits spread across many communities in the Northwest, ranging from 100 - 1000 fighters and their activities cut across kidnapping for ransom, massacre, rape, cattle rustling and violent extremism. It noted that as of December 2022 alone, an estimated 1,087,875 persons have been displaced in rural communities, while about 13,485 persons have been killed as of May 2023 (IPI, 2024). Figure 2 below shows the trend of violent attacks by armed bandits in the northwest region of Nigeria from 2010 to 2023.

Figure 2: Trends of Violent Attacks by Bandits across the Northwest Region from 2010 to May 2023

Source: Ojewale's Compilation from ACLED Database, 2023

Figure 2 above shows the rising incidents of attacks and fatalities in the affected rural communities in Northwest Nigeria from 2010 to 2023. It shows a sporadic increase in 2014 and

a decline from 2015 to 2017, followed by a high increase of up to 2000 incidents in 2018 to over 3,500 incidents in 2022. However, it recorded a decline in both the number of incidents and

fatalities in 2023, which was attributed to the intensification of military offensives that neutralized a large number of bandits and arrested many, while others went into hiding.

Tables 1, 2 and 3 below show the trends of lethal violence-related fatalities across states in the three geopolitical zones in the north from 2006 to 2021.

Table 1: Trend of Lethal Violence-related Deaths in Northeast (2006-2021)

North-east Nigeria	Records of Lethal Violence
Borno	49,692
Adamawa	5,117
Yobe	3,876
Taraba	3,575
Bauchi	2,777
Gombe	1,407
Total	66,444

Source: Author's Compilation from Ukoji, V. & Ukoji, V (2023).

Table 2: Trend of Lethal Violence-related Deaths in North-central (2006-2021)

North-Central Nigeria	Records of Lethal Violence
Plateau	6,470
Benue	6,370
Niger	3,673
Nasarawa	3,340
Abuja (FCT)	3,209
Kogi	2,815
Kwara	1,755
Total	27,632

Source: Author's Compilation from Ukoji, V. & Ukoji, V (2023).

Table 3: Trend of Lethal Violence related Deaths in Northwest (2006-2021)

Northwest Nigeria	Records of Lethal Violence
Kaduna	8,543
Kano	2,803
Katsina	3,477
Kebbi	1,923
Jigawa	1,108

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Sokoto	3,575
Zamfara	6,843
Total	22,113

Source: Author's Compilation from Ukoji, V. & Ukoji, V (2023).

The statistics from tables 1, 2, and 3 show that the three geopolitical zones put together recorded a total of 116,189 deaths from lethal fatalities mostly attributed to attacks from terrorism and banditry related activities, with states like Borno (49,692), Kaduna (8,543), Zamfara (6,843), Plateau (6,470), Benue (6,370), and Adamawa (5,117) taking the lead. The record high of deaths in Borno is attributed to the renewed attacks by Boko Haram terrorists in the state, while that of Kaduna, Zamfara, and Benue is attributed to increasing attacks by armed bandits in the states. The majority of these attacks occurred in the rural communities where the majority of the residents are predominantly farmers.

Based on the foregoing overview of insecurity in the northern region, it is obvious that the insecurity bedevilling the region is caused by the increasing menace of armed banditry and terrorism that have taken over the region, particularly in the rural communities where the agricultural activities take place. Apart from its effects on the livelihood and well-being of the region and its people, it also has a direct impact on Nigeria's food security.

Implications of Insecurity in Northern Nigeria for Food Security in Nigeria

Insecurity in Northern Nigeria significantly undermines national food security by disrupting agricultural activities, fracturing supply chains, displacing millions of farmers, and increasing food prices due to limited access to markets and high transportation costs. This, in turn, leads to greater food security and rising malnutrition rates, especially in vulnerable communities, as people struggle to access sufficient and nutritious food. These are discussed below.

Impact on Food Production and Livelihood

Agriculture is the main supplier of food in Nigeria, supported by importation, and the majority of the supplies come from the northern region of Nigeria, which contributes about 70 per cent of the staple food in Nigeria. It is a significant part of the country's economy, contributing almost 30 per cent of the total GDP and generating employment for about 70 per cent of the labour force (NBS, 2021). Therefore, the consistent incidents of banditry, conflicts, and kidnapping for ransom that have pervaded the rural communities in the north significantly affect food security in Nigeria as a result of the disruption of farming activities. In addition, it has displaced millions of people, particularly in farming states like Benue, Borno, Adamawa, Plateau, Yobe, Katsina, and Zamfara, where the

majority of staple foods are grown, forcing them away from their ancestral farmlands and traditional livelihoods. This has significantly affected food production, in turn impacting negatively on the general food security in Nigeria. The NBS (2023) report further confirmed this when it noted that the estimated food production growth rates declined at 1.36 per cent in the third quarter of 2021, far behind the growth rate of food demand at 6.5 per cent. It further observed that in 2022, the gap between food production growth rates and the growth rate of food demand had increased significantly, resulting in acute food security. This became clearer when the 2023 Global Hunger Index report was released in 2024, which ranked Nigeria 109th out of 125 countries, with a score of 28.3, indicating a serious hunger level (Punch, 2024). Incidentally, the trend has worsened as many households can hardly afford a decent meal. In addition to the problem of food production, access to inputs like seeds and fertilisers has remained a serious challenge for farmers in the north, due to insecurity in the region, further reducing agricultural outputs in the region. At the end, the whole chain of food production and livelihood is affected with a devastating impact on Nigeria's food security.

Impact of Food Supply and Access

Insecurity also damages crucial infrastructure and makes transportation costly and dangerous, disrupting the flow of food from farms to markets. The protracted nature of insecurity in the north has tremendously reduced the number of transporters that ply the route,

leading to the high cost of transporting foodstuffs to other parts of the country for sale, with a significant effect on the food supply chain. The NBS (2023) report, for instance, showed substantial year-on-year increases for items like rice (73.16%), beans (44.99%), and beef (29.61%) from 2017 to 2023, indicating a steep rise in food prices throughout the year. The report identified the factors driving the increasing cost of food prices, including shortage and scarcity of food, high cost of transporting the goods, and insecurity in the northern region. In addition, the 2024 State of Food Security and Nutrition noted that Nigeria faces a dire food security situation, with over 31.8 million people experiencing acute food insecurity, a significant increase from the previous year. It noted that this crisis is driven by conflict and displacement, severe economic instability, including record inflation and devaluation, and climate-related events like droughts and floods. The report observed that an estimated 172 million Nigerians, representing 78.7 per cent of the population, could not afford a healthy diet as of 2022, a trend of increasing numbers since 2017 (Punch, 2024). Sadly, the inflation rate and the low purchasing power of an average Nigerian have made it worse, leading to a lack of accessibility to healthy meals, which in turn has resulted in a high rate of malnutrition among children below the age of 5 years.

Furthermore, the high cost of transportation also affects the quantity of goods that can get to the market. For instance, a farmer will need more money to move the produce to the market,

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and so is the trader, who also needs more money to pay for the goods, including the cost of transporting them to his/her business destination. It also increases post-harvest losses, as many of the goods (mostly perishables) get spoiled with the farmers, due to a lack of capacity to get them to the market. This whole cycle of increase in the cost of movement, in turn, affects the quantity of goods that come into the market, thereby expanding the gap between demand and supply, resulting in a high increase in food prices, which ultimately contributes to worsening the food security crisis.

Impact on Rural-Urban Migration

Another major implication is the forced rural-urban migration in northern Nigeria as a result of the escalating insecurity from groups like the Boko Haram terrorists and bandits, who disrupt agricultural livelihoods and lives, pushing people from rural communities into urban centres in search of safety and a better life. Reports have shown that a high number of youths in rural communities in the north are forced to leave their communities to city centres daily, where there is relative security and peace to engage in menial jobs, motorcycle or tricycle transportation to earn a living. For instance, the UNDP (2022) report on displacements in Nigeria noted that conflict and violence in northern Nigeria led to about 376,000 new displacements in 2021, adding to the more than 3.2 million persons living in displacement at the end of 2020. Similarly, the governor of Zamfara State, one of the most affected states in the

northwest, noted that banditry has led to the displacement of over 700,000 people in the state, the majority of whom are young people, women and children (Kunnuji et al., 2024). Sadly, the number of displaced persons has continued to increase not only in Zamfara but in other affected states in the region, resulting in the depletion of the labour force needed for farming in the rural communities. On the other hand, it is increasing the number of people in the urban centres with little or no agricultural farms, straining distribution systems, placing more demands on food supply, and leading to high food scarcity and high food prices that make nutritious food less accessible to the urban poor, who are heavily dependent on purchased foods. This is evident in the increasing number of beggars on the streets of Nigeria's state capitals, including Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), particularly women, children and young people.

Humanitarian Consequences

Disruptions to food production and access driven by factors like conflict, banditry, and terrorism lead to a significant jump in the number of people facing acute hunger and malnutrition, with a severe spike in cases among children, forced displacement, and a decline in livelihoods. This dislocation in the livelihood of people pushes more people into poverty and necessitates increased humanitarian aid. Figure 3 below shows the statistics from the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization on the increasing trend in the number of people at risk of food insecurity over seven years:

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Figure 3: Number of moderately and severely food-insecure people, millions, 3-year average, 2014-2022

Source: United Nations Food and Agriculture Organisation (2022).

Remarkably, the data reveal that the number of people who are food insecure escalated from 63 million individuals in 2016 to a staggering 148.7 million in 2022. This high progression underscores the urgent need for targeted interventions and sustainable strategies to tackle the worsening challenges of food security in Nigeria. In addition, the 2025 FOA report on Nigeria revealed that an estimated 30.6 million people faced acute food and nutrition insecurity as of June-August 2025, with 1.8 million children at risk of severe acute malnutrition. This critical situation is a result of escalating conflict, banditry, terrorism, and economic instability, particularly affecting the northeast, northwest and northcentral regions. Additionally, an estimated 5.4 million children and 800,000 pregnant and breastfeeding women were reported to be at risk of acute malnutrition or wasting, and may require critical nutrition treatment to survive (UN News, 2024). This has exacerbated the already existing

humanitarian challenge in Nigeria, putting more pressure on the government and its international humanitarian partners to provide humanitarian assistance in the country.

Conclusion

The study has critically examined the insecurity in Northern Nigeria and its implications for food security in Nigeria, noting that insecurity in Northern Nigeria, which is triggered by a combination of criminalities by non-state armed groups, including radical Islamic terrorists and extremist groups like Boko Haram, ISWAP, Lakurawa, armed bandits, and killer herders, has inflicted significant damage in the region. The study revealed that the incessant violent attacks that have resulted in the killing of thousands of residents, sacking of farming communities, destruction of farmlands and displacement of millions of people in the region have had significant adverse effects on food security across the country.

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E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 7.80

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

The study noted that the Northern region, which is Nigeria's largest producer of agricultural produce, contributing over 70 per cent of the country's staple food, has all of a sudden been associated with poor agricultural yields, poverty and hunger, with the majority of its farming communities displaced from their ancestral homes to neighbouring states or refugee camps due to insecurity. This, the study noted, has not only affected the northern region, but the generality of the country. Using the global health diet report of the United Nations, the study noted that currently, about 172 million Nigerians, representing 78.7 per cent of the population, could not afford a healthy diet, a trend which has continued to increase despite government efforts at addressing the insecurity.

The study highlighted some of the major implications for food security in Nigeria to include shortage in food production and decline agricultural livelihood, decline in food supply and access, rural-urban migration, and humanitarian consequences, noting that insecurity in the northern region has exposed the strength and weaknesses of Nigeria's security architecture, which the federal government and its national security managers should engage in efforts aimed at enhancing Nigeria's national security architecture that would guarantee the security of lives of citizens. The study, therefore, suggests that the federal government, in collaboration with the state governments in the north, should adopt a multi-

faceted approach that combines kinetic and non-kinetic approaches to ensure the return of peace and security in the region. Additionally, emphasis should also be laid on encouraging young people into agriculture and supporting existing farmers through sustainable agriculture policies such as modern practices, empowering smallholder farmers with credit and technology, strengthening food value chains with storage and processing, and implementing supportive policies and social protection programs, fostering public-private partnerships, investing in security and promoting youth engagement in farming. This approach, if adopted, would ensure the security of the people, encourage the return of displaced farmers and improve agricultural productivity for enhanced food security in Nigeria.

Recommendations

To ensure sustained peace and security, which would stimulate agricultural productivity in northern Nigeria, it is recommended that

1. The federal government of Nigeria should ensure that collaboration between security agencies, community leaders, and local informants is enhanced to improve intelligence gathering, threat detection, and conflict prevention.
2. The federal government, in collaboration with the state governments, should strengthen peace-building initiatives to address the socio-economic grievances

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fuelling insecurity across affected communities. Such efforts should be coordinated through peace organizations like the Peace and Reconciliation Commission in Benue State and Plateau Peace Building Agency (PPBA) and supervised by the Office of the National Security Adviser.

3. State governments, non-governmental organisations and international partners should work closely with the military joint task force operations in the region to implement peacebuilding initiatives, provide humanitarian assistance, and facilitate long-term development projects, such as roads, electricity, water supply, and ICT infrastructure.
4. State governments should show commitment towards the containment of insecurity in their various states by complementing the efforts of the security agencies, through financial support for logistics and supplies of modern military equipment, like modern surveillance tools, communication systems, and providing intelligence on high-risk areas.
5. The federal government in collaboration with state governments in the region should adopt the use of psychological operational tactics (PYSOPs), using local media houses, social media handles such as influential bloggers, local celebrities and moderate clerics to weaken the

influence of the criminal groups on the local population and to win their hearts and minds of the locals towards supporting the mission. This should also be backed by socio-economic programmes and initiatives, such as employment creation, skill acquisition programmes, and youth empowerment schemes, to address the socio-economic factors driving these challenges.

6. The federal government should put in measures to ensure the effective control of small arms and light weapons proliferation in the region, through enlightenment campaigns using psychological operational tactics, involving respected religious and community leaders in the affected areas.

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